

ALGEBRAIK TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASINI YECHISH

To‘yliyev Abbos

DTPI talabasi

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Biz quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasini yechishni qaraylik.

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = a_{1n+1} \\ a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + \dots + a_{2n}x_n = a_{2n+1} \\ \dots \\ a_{n1}x_1 + a_{n2}x_2 + \dots + a_{nn}x_n = a_{nn+1} \end{cases}$$

Tenglamalar sistemasini yechishning quyidagi usulini qaraylik. Sodda uchun 4 nomalumli 4 ta tenglamadan iborat bo‘lgan sistemani qaraymiz.

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + a_{13}x_3 + a_{14}x_4 = a_{15} \\ a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + a_{23}x_3 + a_{24}x_4 = a_{25} \\ a_{31}x_1 + a_{32}x_2 + a_{33}x_3 + a_{34}x_4 = a_{35} \\ a_{41}x_1 + a_{42}x_2 + a_{43}x_3 + a_{44}x_4 = a_{45} \end{cases}$$

(1) tenglamalar sistemasini barcha tenglamalarini mos ravishda x_1 no‘malumni oldidagi koefitsiyentga bo‘lib yuboramiz. Natijada quyidagi tenglamalar sistemi kelib chiqadi:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + \frac{a_{12}}{a_{11}}x_2 + \frac{a_{13}}{a_{11}}x_3 + \frac{a_{14}}{a_{11}}x_4 = \frac{a_{15}}{a_{11}} \\ x_1 + \frac{a_{22}}{a_{21}}x_2 + \frac{a_{23}}{a_{21}}x_3 + \frac{a_{24}}{a_{21}}x_4 = \frac{a_{25}}{a_{21}} \\ x_1 + \frac{a_{32}}{a_{31}}x_2 + \frac{a_{33}}{a_{31}}x_3 + \frac{a_{34}}{a_{31}}x_4 = \frac{a_{35}}{a_{31}} \\ x_1 + \frac{a_{42}}{a_{41}}x_2 + \frac{a_{43}}{a_{41}}x_3 + \frac{a_{44}}{a_{41}}x_4 = \frac{a_{45}}{a_{41}} \end{cases}$$

Ushbu sistemadan

$$\frac{a_{ni}}{a_{n1}} = a_{ni}^{(1)} \quad n = 1,2,3,4; \quad i = 2,3,4,5$$

deb belgilash olamiz. Natijada quyidagi sistema hosil bo‘ladi:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + a_{12}^{(1)}x_2 + a_{13}^{(1)}x_3 + a_{14}^{(1)}x_4 = a_{15}^{(1)} \\ x_1 + a_{22}^{(1)}x_2 + a_{23}^{(1)}x_3 + a_{24}^{(1)}x_4 = a_{25}^{(1)} \\ x_1 + a_{32}^{(1)}x_2 + a_{33}^{(1)}x_3 + a_{34}^{(1)}x_4 = a_{35}^{(1)} \\ x_1 + a_{42}^{(1)}x_2 + a_{43}^{(1)}x_3 + a_{44}^{(1)}x_4 = a_{45}^{(1)} \end{cases}$$

Bu sistemani 1-tenglamasidan 2-3-4-tenglamalarini ayiramiz, va

$a_{1n}^{(1)} - a_{in}^{(1)} = a_{in}^{(1*)}$ ($n = 2,3,4,5 \quad i = 2,3,4$) deb belgilash olsak, quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasini hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + a_{12}^{(1)}x_2 + a_{13}^{(1)}x_3 + a_{14}^{(1)}x_4 = a_{15}^{(1)} \\ a_{22}^{(1*)}x_2 + a_{23}^{(1*)}x_3 + a_{24}^{(1*)}x_4 = a_{25}^{(1*)} \\ a_{32}^{(1*)}x_2 + a_{33}^{(1*)}x_3 + a_{34}^{(1*)}x_4 = a_{35}^{(1*)} \\ a_{42}^{(1*)}x_2 + a_{43}^{(1*)}x_3 + a_{44}^{(1*)}x_4 = a_{45}^{(1*)} \end{cases}$$

hosil bo‘lgan tenglamalar sistemasini 2-3-4- tenglamalarini x_2 no‘malumini oldidagi koefitsiyentga bo‘lib yuboramiz va

$$\frac{a_{ni}^{(1*)}}{a_{n2}^{(1*)}} = a_{ni}^{(2)} \quad (n = 2,3,4; \quad i = 3,4,5)$$

belgilash olamiz, natijada tenglamamiz quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + a_{12}^{(1)} x_2 + a_{13}^{(1)} x_3 + a_{14}^{(1)} x_4 = a_{15}^{(1)} \\ x_2 + a_{23}^{(2)} x_3 + a_{24}^{(2)} x_4 = a_{25}^{(2)} \\ x_2 + a_{33}^{(2)} x_3 + a_{34}^{(2)} x_4 = a_{35}^{(2)} \\ x_2 + a_{43}^{(2)} x_3 + a_{44}^{(2)} x_4 = a_{45}^{(2)} \end{cases}$$

Hosil bo'lgan tenglamalar sistemasida 2-tenglamasidan 3-4-tenglamalarini ayiramiz va $a_{2n}^{(2)} - a_{in}^{(2)} = a_{in}^{(2*)}$ ($n = 3,4,5 \quad i = 3,4$) deb belgilash olib, quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasini hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + a_{12}^{(1)} x_2 + a_{13}^{(1)} x_3 + a_{14}^{(1)} x_4 = a_{15}^{(1)} \\ x_2 + a_{23}^{(2)} x_3 + a_{24}^{(2)} x_4 = a_{25}^{(2)} \\ a_{33}^{(2*)} x_3 + a_{34}^{(2*)} x_4 = a_{35}^{(2*)} \\ a_{43}^{(2*)} x_3 + a_{44}^{(2*)} x_4 = a_{45}^{(2*)} \end{cases}$$

hosil bo'lgan sistemani 3- va 4- tenglamalarini x_3 no'malumini oldidagi koeffitsiyentiga bo'lib yuboramiz va

$$\frac{a_{ni}^{(2*)}}{a_{n3}^{(2*)}} = a_{ni}^{(3)} \quad (n = 3,4; \quad i = 4,5)$$

belgilash olib, quyidagi sistemani hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + a_{12}^{(1)} x_2 + a_{13}^{(1)} x_3 + a_{14}^{(1)} x_4 = a_{15}^{(1)} \\ x_2 + a_{23}^{(2)} x_3 + a_{24}^{(2)} x_4 = a_{25}^{(2)} \\ x_3 + a_{34}^{(3)} x_4 = a_{35}^{(3)} \\ x_3 + a_{44}^{(3)} x_4 = a_{45}^{(3)} \end{cases}$$

Hosil bo'lgan sistemani 3-tenglamasidan 4-tenglamasini ayiramiz va $a_{3n}^{(3)} - a_{in}^{(3)} = a_{in}^{(3*)}$ $n = 4,5; \quad i = 4$ belgilash olsak, quyidagi sistema hosil bo'ladi:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + a_{12}^{(1)} x_2 + a_{13}^{(1)} x_3 + a_{14}^{(1)} x_4 = a_{15}^{(1)} \\ x_2 + a_{23}^{(2)} x_3 + a_{24}^{(2)} x_4 = a_{25}^{(2)} \\ x_3 + a_{34}^{(3)} x_4 = a_{35}^{(3)} \\ a_{44}^{(3*)} x_4 = a_{45}^{(3*)} \end{cases}$$

hosil bo'lgan sistemaning 4-tenglamasidan x_4 ni topsak,

$$x_4 = \frac{a_{45}^{(3*)}}{a_{44}^{(3*)}} = a_{45}^{(4)}$$

ekanligini topib olamiz. Endi teskarisidan boorish usulini qo'llab x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 larni topamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} x_4 &= a_{45}^{(4)} \\ x_3 &= a_{35}^{(3)} - a_{34}^{(3)} a_{45}^{(4)} \\ x_2 &= a_{25}^{(2)} - a_{24}^{(2)} a_{45}^{(4)} - a_{23}^{(2)} (a_{35}^{(3)} - a_{34}^{(3)} a_{45}^{(4)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$x_1 = a_{15}^{(1)} - a_{14}^{(1)} a_{45}^{(4)} - a_{13}^{(1)} (a_{35}^{(3)} - a_{34}^{(3)} a_{45}^{(4)}) - a_{12}^{(1)} (a_{25}^{(2)} - a_{24}^{(2)} a_{45}^{(4)} - a_{23}^{(2)} (a_{35}^{(3)} - a_{34}^{(3)} a_{45}^{(4)}))$$

Misol. Quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasini yeching:

$$\begin{cases} 6,1x_1 + 6,2x_2 - 6,3x_3 + 6,4x_4 = 6,5 \\ 1,1x_1 - 1,5x_2 + 2,2x_3 - 3,8x_4 = 4,2 \\ 5,1x_1 - 5,0x_2 + 4,9x_3 - 4,8x_4 = 4,7 \\ 1,8x_1 + 1,9x_2 + 2,0x_3 - 2,1x_4 = 2,2 \end{cases}$$

Ushbu tenglamalar sistemasini yechish uchun jadvaldan foydalanamiz:

	a_{i1}	a_{i2}	a_{i3}	a_{i4}	a_{i5}
a_{1i}	6,1	6,2	-6,3	6,4	6,5
a_{2i}	1,1	-1,5	2,2	-3,8	4,2
a_{3i}	5,1	-5,0	4,9	-4,8	4,7
a_{4i}	1,8	1,9	2,0	-2,1	2,2

$a_{1i}^{(1)}$	1	1,0164	-1,0328	1,0492	1,0656
$a_{2i}^{(1)}$	1	-1,3636	2	-3,4545	3,8182
$a_{3i}^{(1)}$	1	-0,9804	0,9608	-0,9412	0,9216
$a_{4i}^{(1)}$	1	1,0556	1,1111	-1,1667	1,2222

$a_{1i}^{(1*)}$	1	1,0164	-1,0328	1,0492	1,0656
$a_{2i}^{(1*)}$	0	2,38	-3,0328	4,5037	-2,7526
$a_{3i}^{(1*)}$	0	1,9968	-1,9936	1,9904	0,144
$a_{4i}^{(1*)}$	0	-0,0392	-2,1439	2,2159	-0,1566

$a_{1i}^{(2)}$	1	1,0164	-1,0328	1,0492	1,0656
$a_{2i}^{(2)}$	0	1	-1,2743	1,8923	-1,1566
$a_{3i}^{(2)}$	0	1	-0,9984	0,9968	0,0721
$a_{4i}^{(2)}$	0	1	54,6913	-56,5281	3,9949

$a_{1i}^{(2*)}$	1	1,0164	-1,0328	1,0492	1,0656
$a_{2i}^{(2*)}$	0	1	-1,2743	1,8923	-1,1566
$a_{3i}^{(2*)}$	0	0	-0,2759	0,8955	-1,2287
$a_{4i}^{(2*)}$	0	0	-55,9656	58,4204	-5,1515

$a_{1i}^{(3)}$	1	1,0164	-1,0328	1,0492	1,0656
$a_{2i}^{(3)}$	0	1	-1,2743	1,8923	-1,1566
$a_{3i}^{(3)}$	0	0	1	-3,2457	4,4534
$a_{4i}^{(3)}$	0	0	1	-1,0439	0,0921

$a_{1i}^{(3*)}$	1	1,0164	-1,0328	1,0492	1,0656
$a_{2i}^{(3*)}$	0	1	-1,2743	1,8923	-1,1566
$a_{3i}^{(3*)}$	0	0	1	-3,2457	4,4534
$a_{3i}^{(3*)}$	0	0	0	-2,2018	4,3613

$$-2,2018x_4 = 4,3613$$

$$x_4 = -1,9808 = a_{4i}^{(4)}$$

$$x_3 = 4,4534 - (-3,2457) * -1,9808 = -1,9757$$

$$x_2 = -1,1566 - 1,8923 * (-1,9808) - (-1,2743) * (-1,9757) = 0,0740$$

$$x_1 = 1,0656 - 1,0492 * (-1,9808) - (-1,0328) * (-1,9757) - 1,0164 * 0,0740 = 1,0281$$

$$\text{Javob: } x_1 = 1,0281; x_2 = 0,0740; x_3 = -1,9757; x_4 = -1,9808.$$

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